

TABLE 1—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES AT $\mu=1.0 M$ POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

	Nd(III)	Hydrazine 1:1		Hydroxylamine 1:1		Phenylhydrazine 1:1	
		25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°
Metal-ligand stability constants (log k)	Nd(III)	4.97	4.12	3.87	3.55	3.42	3.13
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in k cal/mole	Nd(III)	-10.59*		-18.09*		-12.24*	
Change in free energy (ΔG) in k cal/mole	Nd(III)	-5.99	-5.83	-5.30	-5.04	-4.69	-4.43
Change in entropy (ΔS) in cal/degree/mole	Nd(III)	-12.46	-15.61	-26.13	-26.39	-25.93	-25.36

The order of stability constants was found to be
 $Nd(O_2H_2NH_2)^{2+} < Nd(NH_2OH)^{2+} < Nd(N_2H_4)^{2+}$.

* For the difference of 10°.

plexes of Nd(III) with these derivative of ammonia on a dropping mercury electrode have been studied and the results are presented here.

Experimental

A. R. grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions. The solutions of ligands were prepared by dissolving the calculated quantities of hydrazine hydrochloride, hydroxylamine hydrochloride and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (Chroma-Gesellschaft Schmid and Co., Germany) in double distilled water. The metal solution was prepared by dissolving the metal oxide in hydrochloric acid and was standardized with EDTA⁵.

In the test electrolytic solution, the concentrations of Nd(III), potassium chloride and gelatin were 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. The concentration of ligand was varied from 1.0 mM to 10.0 mM in each case. Ionic strength was fixed at $\mu=1.0$ adjusted with potassium chloride. Sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid was used to adjust the pH of the test solution at 2.4 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording (C.I.C., Baroda, India) polarograph, the capillary used had an in value of 2.15 mg/sec, and drop time of 3.1 sec at 44.0 cm effective height of the mercury ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.15 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$). Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for removing the dissolved oxygen. An Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120) was used to measure the pH of the solution. All the measurements were carried out at 25 and 35° by the use of a thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Nd(III) gives a well defined three electron reversible reduction wave at pH $2.4 \pm 0.02^{6-7}$ in 1.0 M potassium chloride, with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The log plot slopes comes to the order of 20 ± 1 mV for Nd(III) and its complexes with all the three ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The nature of the waves for metal ion and its complexes was found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs \sqrt{t} . The reduction potential of Nd(III) at pH 2.40 ± 0.02 was -1.79 V vs SCE.

The half wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand. A

Lingane⁸ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1:1 complexes of Nd(III) with all the three ligands. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated from the thermodynamic relations⁹ and are given in Table 1.

Hydrazine is more basic¹⁰⁻¹¹ than hydroxylamine. This explains the higher stability of $Nd(N_2H_4)^{2+}$ than $Nd(NH_2OH)^{2+}$. The heavy benzene nucleus in phenylhydrazine is responsible for the lesser stability of its complex with Nd(III).

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Dielectric and Ultraviolet Studies of Molecular Complexes in *n*-Butanol-Carbonyl Systems

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GENERALLY, the short range interactions like hydrogen bonding between a proton donor and an acceptor lead to an increased polarity of the bond¹ and hence the dipole moment of the adduct will

differ from the vector sum of the components. This enhancement of the dipole moment, $\Delta\mu$ defined as

$\Delta\mu = \mu_{\text{complex}} - (\mu_a + \mu_b)$ can be used to study the nature of the hydrogen bond formed. Several investigators²⁻⁵ have determined the $\Delta\mu$ values for a number of systems and these values are attributed either to the tautomeric equilibrium between molecular and ion pair species or to the delocalization of electrons leading to charge transfer. The latter model has been strengthened with the various observed correlations⁶⁻⁹ connecting the $\Delta\mu$ with pK_a , ΔH and ionization potential values. The observation of a new band, characteristic of charge transfer by Nagakura *et al.*^{10,11} in the ultraviolet region is the direct experimental evidence in favour of this model. Presently the dielectric polarization measurements and ultraviolet absorption study of a few *n*-butanol carbonyl systems have been carried out to study the nature of the complexes formed in these systems.

Experimental

The WTW dipolemeter was used for the dielectric measurement at 2 MHz. The refractive index measurements have been carried out in an Abbe refractometer. The cell temperature was maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with Coloro ultrathermostat. Carbon tetrachloride was used as solvent.

Ultraviolet absorption spectra were recorded with a Perkin Elmer 554 UV-VIS double beam recording microcomputer controlled spectrophotometer. Quartz cells with one cm path length were used. Cyclohexane was taken as solvent. Keeping the carbonyl concentration constant, the butanol concentration was increased in steps.

Results and Discussion

The dielectric measurements indicated the presence of the 1:1 complexes in the systems studied¹². The dipole moments of the 1:1 complexes were determined by the methods of Few and Smith¹³ and Huyskens *et al.*^{14,15} and the values are given in Table 1 along with the dipole moment values of the carbonyls. The most favourable position for maximum interaction to occur between the lone pair atomic dipole and the O-H bond is

that position for which the hydrogen bonds formed by the carbonyl compounds should be along sp^2 lone pair direction of the carbonyl group¹⁶. This means that the angle between the carbonyl axis and O-H bond should be 60° . Schuster¹⁷, with his LCAO-MO studies of the hydrogen bonding between carbonyl and hydroxyl groups showed that for structures with the same orientation of the functional groups forming the hydrogen bond the arrangement with the smaller dipole moment has the lower energy¹⁸. From these points and from the calculated dipole moment values for both the *trans* and *cis* forms (Table 1) it can be concluded that the *trans* form is the most suitable one for *n*-butanol-carbonyl complexes¹⁹. For acetone-*n*-butanol system the favourable structure is given in Fig. 1. Knowing

Fig. 1. 1:1 Adduct of *n*-butanol-acetone.

the geometrical structures of the complexes, the enhancement of dipole moment $\Delta\mu$ values are determined²⁰ and are given in Table 1. The $\Delta\mu_{\text{ind}}$ values due to induced polarization effect for the systems studied calculated by Frank method²¹ are of the order 0.1 D to 0.15 D. As these values are found to be less than the presently calculated $\Delta\mu$ values, it is reasonable to expect a charge transfer as envisaged by Ratajczak *et al.*^{3,7,8}, i.e. $\Delta\mu = \Delta\mu_{\text{ind}} + \Delta\mu_{\text{CT}}$. This charge transfer should result in a new absorption band in the ultraviolet region. The spectra recorded for these systems in the region 2000 to 9000 Å do not show any such band which will ascertain the EDA nature of the hydrogen bonds in these systems. Probably the vacuum ultraviolet studies may confirm this as in the case of acetic acid-amine system¹¹. The formation of hydrogen

TABLE 1—THE DIPOLE MOMENT VALUES OF THE 1:1 COMPLEXES FORMED BETWEEN *n*-BUTANOL AND A FEW CARBONYL COMPOUNDS DETERMINED BY VARIOUS METHODS AND THE ENHANCEMENT OF DIPOLE MOMENT VALUES

System	μ_b (D)	Dipole moment values determined by			Average μ_{ab} (D)	Dipole Moment calculated for		θ_b	$\Delta\mu$ (D)
		Few and Smith Method (D)	Huyskens <i>et al.</i> Method I (D)	Method II (D)		<i>Trans</i> form (D)	<i>Cis</i> form (D)		
<i>n</i> -Butanol +									
1. Acetone	2.70	3.50	3.21	3.23	3.31	2.90	4.34	60°	0.44
2. Ethyl methyl ketone	2.68	3.48	3.19	3.22	3.30	2.88	4.32	60°	0.45
3. Cyclohexanone	2.80	3.67	3.36	3.47	3.50	2.98	4.44	60°	0.56
4. Acetophenone	2.76	3.63	3.30	3.34	3.42	2.74	4.35	$67'35''$	0.75

$\mu_a = 1.7\text{D}$; $\theta_a = 41^\circ$.

bond with n -electron lowers the frequency of the n -orbital by an amount equal to the energy of the hydrogen bond. The frequency shifts ($\Delta\nu$) observed and the energy values ($\Delta E = h\Delta\nu$) calculated are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THE FREQUENCIES OF THE CHROMOPHORE WHEN IT IS FREE AND COMPLEXED WITH BUTANOL, IN VARIOUS n -BUTANOL CARBONYL SYSTEMS

System	Free ν_f cm ⁻¹	Bonded ν_b cm ⁻¹	Blue Shift $\Delta\nu$ cm ⁻¹	ΔE Kcals/mole
n -Butanol + Acetone	35,971	36,550	579	1.65
Ethyl methyl ketone	35,971	36,364	393	1.12
Cyclohexanone	34,433	35,112	629	1.80
Acetophenone	31,368	31,746	378	1.08

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Epoxidation of α,β -Unsaturated Aldehydes and Esters

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A systematic study of the kinetics of epoxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones with alkaline hydrogen peroxide in methanol medium has been carried out recently¹ and similar studies have been extended to α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and esters. Such a study will give one an insight into the mechanism of epoxidation in non-aqueous solvents and would also permit a comparison of the reactivity of the $>C=O$ group when attached to a $>C=C<$ linkage during epoxidation. Recently, there have been reports of successful alkaline epoxidations of cinnamaldehyde, crotonaldehyde and citral under controlled pH conditions².

On the other hand the epoxidation of unsaturated esters of cinnamic and crotonic acids has been carried out with several peroxy-acids in a variety of solvents and the rates of epoxidation have been reported³. However, to this date, there has been no report in the literature on the study of the kinetics of epoxidation of α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and esters using alkaline hydrogen peroxide. Hence a systematic study of the epoxidation of these compounds has been carried out.

Experimental

Cinnamaldehyde, crotonaldehyde, citral, methyl and ethyl crotonates and methyl and ethyl cinnamates (Flüka, extra pure) were employed.

Epoxy methyl and ethyl crotonate and epoxy ethyl cinnamate were prepared⁴ and used for comparison of the R_f values (Table 1) with those of the products isolated soon after the kinetic studies. Epoxides of cinnamaldehyde and crotonaldehyde were separated by tlc and identified as their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES AT 30°
SOLVENT: BENZENE-METHYL ACETATE (2:1)

Compound	Substrate	Epoxide
Cinnamaldehyde	0.51	0.23
Crotonaldehyde	0.55	0.23
Ethyl crotonate	0.60	0.34
Methyl crotonate	0.71	0.18
Ethyl cinnamate	0.48	0.27
*Benzaldehyde	0.63	—
*Acetaldehyde	0.19	—

*Values used to check up the fission products of epoxy cinnamaldehyde and epoxy crotonaldehyde.

UV and tlc techniques have been employed for the kinetic and analytical studies. TLC has been